

Potential of herpetofauna in traditional medicine, geographic distribution and new record of endemic *Ichthyophis elongatus* in West Sumatra.

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Mapping and the potential distribution of animals are closely related to the field of animal ecology, through an ecological approach we can determine how the habitat or niche is suitable for an animal. so that its natural availability is maintained. fields that are suitable for collaborating with this field are phylogeographic, ethnozoology and taxonomy. The results obtained by mixing these fields are that some animals from herpetofauna are used for traditional medicine in West Sumatra by looking at and reviewing the geographic potential and new records in West Sumatra, especially endemic animals. This study is not very common, especially in today's era where many have turned to modern medicine. However, with the richness of ethnicity and biodiversity in Indonesia, it is necessary to pay attention to it. it is also very useful to be the basis or basis for modern medical research that refers to traditional medicine. In this article, the phylogeographic, taxonomic and ethnozoological studies are herpetofauna, some of which are endemic to the region of West Sumatra.

Herpetofauna comes from corn, the word herpeton, which means reptiles. In the past, before taxonomy developed, Reptiles are included in one group of animals because they are considered to be both reptiles from amphibians. With the development of science, they are now two separate groups. These two groups belong to one field, namely herpetology because they have a way of life from almost similar habitats, both are ectothermal vertebrates (requires an external heat source), and methods for the observer's arms (Kusrini, et al., 2008). Reptiles have long been used by the community. For example, snakes are fauna resources that are widely used as one of the most common commodities have high economic value. Snakes are used, among others, as material for medical experiments, pets, craft materials (bags, shoes, belts, etc.) and for consumption (Situngkir, 2009). Furthermore, the questionnaire used for In West Sumatra can find traditional medicine at each quota, but there is not much information that is different from the one selected. In terms of traditional medicine in other areas, such as the results of the 1995 Susenas which explained the use of traditional medicine by the community for treatment in DKI Jakarta 2.76%, DI Yogyakarta 3.19%, East Java 5.59%. The results of the Susenas can be evidence that traditional medicine is still widely used by people from certain circles, including intellectuals (Santoso, 1998). Amphibians also provide benefits to humans, such as as a source of animal protein or direct benefits as part of the food chain. Millet skin secretions of several types of amphibians have also been developed as antibiotics from painkillers (Stebbins and Cohen, 1995).

One type of species from the herpetofauna group which is endemic and found in West Sumatra and is rarely known, namely *Ichthyophis elongatus*. *Ichthyophis elongatus* Taylor, 1965, is only known from the type locality in Padang, West Sumatra. This species is considered Data Deficient by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group 2018). In addition, no single occurrence is available at the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (<https://www.gbif.org/>) and publications on the species do not have geographic coordinates (Teynie et al. 2010). To support sampling efforts in the field, the maximum entropy algorithm (Phillips et al. 2006; Elith et al. 2011) was used to identify the

potential distribution of *Ichthyophis elongatus*. MaxEnt software was chosen because it provides satisfactory predictions with a small number of events (Yi et al. 2016; Ramos and Torres 2011; Adhikari et al. 2012; Yang et al. 2013; Padalia et al. 2014; Remya et al. 2015; According to Yuan et al. 2015; Pranata et al. 2019). The map generated from MaxEnt can be useful for further studies on *I. elongatus* in particular and other Sumatran in general. Predicted distribution based on entropy modelling maximum indicates a highly suitable habitat for the species throughout the Barisan Mountains at 500–1000 m above sea level. Our model suggests swamps, rice fields, and secondary forest 100–150 m from the river as the highest habitat for the species. Further surveys in the two regions predicted by the model found new species population.

The research method used in researching the potential of herpetofauna in traditional medicine is the survey method from questionnaires and direct documents. Traditional medicines are ingredients or ingredients of plant materials, animal ingredients, mineral ingredients, field extract preparations (Sugiyono, 2007). The survey was conducted to see the presence of informants to obtain information about the use of herpetofauna as ingredients of traditional medicine. Furthermore, questionnaires were used to obtain information on millet informants who used herpetofauna as ingredients of traditional medicine (Sundari, 2011). The informants selected to be interviewed are traditional medicine sellers in shops from traditional medicine sellers at street vendors. Meanwhile, research on new records and potential geographic distribution, especially *Ichthyophis elongatus* and elongated caecilian endemic to West Sumatra, was carried out with field surveys and recording of ecological parameters. We conducted field surveys in four areas in West Sumatra: Padang (5–8 August 2017), Solok (20 December 2018), Tanah Datar (6–9 March 2019), and Pasaman (20–24 February 2020). We actively search for caecilians by digging the soil with a hoe, turning rocks, leaf litter, and rotting plants, during the day (09:00 – 16:00). The target habitats are garbage dumps, rice fields, riverbanks, and secondary forests. and also the method used. Morphological measurements. Specimens euthanized with tricaine methanesulfonate (MS-222), fixed with 10% formalin and stored in 70% ethanol. following the morphological measurements and diagnosis established by Taylor (1965) to identify the species as *I. elongatus*. After that, the species distribution modeling (HR) was carried out. by using the GeoCat Redlisting tool (Bachman et al. 2011) to assess the extinction risk of *I. elongatus* based on our combined field survey data. then make a distribution map and finally validate the field survey.

It can be concluded by looking at the existing data and literacy that the species *Ichthyophis elongatus* has little study on the geographical distribution. Thus, it is difficult to study the potential possessed by *Ichthyophis elongatus* and conservation. The potential of herpetofauna as an ingredient of traditional medicine varies from region to region West Sumatra, each region has its own beliefs. West Sumatran people who still use traditional medicine with ingredients from one of the genus *Ichthyophis* groups which are included in the herpetofauna group become a separate problem. Especially endemic animal species that are very easy to be threatened with extinction. Their survival is very dependent on the habitat which is an important factor for these animals. the two methods and approaches used to determine the distribution of geographic potential and its potential as traditional medicine are both carried out in the field and in the same area, namely West Sumatra and mutual fallows are important factors for these animals. The two methods and approaches used to determine the distribution of geographic potential and its potential as traditional medicine are both carried out in the field

and in the same area, namely West Sumatra and are interconnected. knowing the potential for geographic distribution and the record of new endemic animals and the potential of these animals as traditional medicines in the community. conservation efforts and interior studies on traditional medicine can be carried out without harming any aspect and will produce solutions for the conservation and potential of herpetofauna in traditional medicine.

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